

Smart Parking System: A Simple Way to Manage Parking Area Using Internet of Things

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Abstract : The need for parking spots has increased as a result of cities' fast urbanisation and rising population, particularly in congested locations like theatres, malls, and other well-liked tourist attractions. The use of a smart parking system has been highly praised as a solution to these problems. This system makes use of Infrared (IR) sensors as well as other cutting-edge technologies to locate and reserve parking spaces, giving drivers up-to-the-minute information on available places. Additionally, the Smart Parking System makes it possible to monitor and manage parking spaces effectively, improving safety and traffic flow. This technology improves customer happiness by decreasing the time and fuel used to hunt for parking and helps to create a more sustainable urban environment.

Keywords: Smart Parking System, parking spaces, Infrared (IR) sensors, slot availability, traffic management, customer satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Smart parking systems are a type of intelligent transportation that uses technology and other factors to help drivers find parking slots easily and efficiently. Smart parking systems use sensor-based technology. The rapid urbanization and increasing population in cities have led to a higher demand for parking spaces, particularly in crowded areas such as theaters, shopping malls, and other popular destinations. To address these challenges, the implementation of a Smart Parking System has gained significant appreciation. This technology utilizes a combination of Infrared (IR) sensors and other advanced technologies to detect and reserve available parking spots, providing drivers with real-time information on slot availability. Furthermore, the Smart Parking System enables efficient monitoring and management of parking spaces, leading to improved traffic flow and enhanced safety. By reducing the time and fuel consumed in searching for parking, this system enhances customer satisfaction and contributes to a more sustainable urban environment. Technology to monitor and track available spaces in real-time, it uses a sequence of Infrared sensors or a individual sensors in each of the slots which allows the drivers to see which spots are available and navigate directly to them. These systems can also improve the parking experience for both drivers and parking officials. Smart parking systems also allow drivers to reserve spots in advance, by displaying the number of available slots in the entrance display or we can also display the slot availability by connecting with the mobile applications. It can reduce the traffic congestion and also helps to save drivers time and money. And they can also provide data on parking trends, allowing cities to better manage their parking resources [1]-[5]. Smart vehicle parking systems leverage the power of Internet of Things (IoT) technology to revolutionize parking management and enhance the overall parking experience for users. These systems utilize a network of sensors, communication devices, and data analytics to provide real-time information on parking space availability, optimize parking resource allocation, and streamline the parking process. By integrating advanced technologies, such as sensor networks, cloud computing, and mobile applications, smart parking systems enable drivers to easily access information about available parking spaces, reserve spots in advance, and navigate to their designated parking locations.

In this paper is to present the results of implementing a smart vehicle parking system that offers real-time access to parking availability and efficient parking management. The system aims to provide a simple, common, efficient, and affordable solution that can be applied to various parking areas. By examining the effectiveness and feasibility of the system, this study aims to shed light on the benefits and potential of smart parking systems in improving parking infrastructure and enhancing user satisfaction.

The main motive behind this technology is to reduce and secure the parking issues in metro cities. The technology is designed to solve the daily problems of parking in many places like malls, multiplex, award functions, auditorium etc. The aim and purpose is to scale down an efficient working model of a vehicle parking system for accommodating vehicles within a limited area [6]-[9].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lee et al [10] provides a comprehensive review of the various technologies and applications employed in Smart Parking Systems. It explores the latest advancements and their impact on improving parking management efficiency and customer experience. Cheng et al [11] Focusing on Internet of Things (IoT)-based Smart Parking

Systems, this review examines the technologies and implementation strategies used in such systems. It discusses the benefits of IoT integration and highlights real-world applications of IoT in smart parking. The Singh et al [12] provides an overview of recent advances in Smart Parking Systems and outlines future research directions. It discusses emerging technologies, such as sensor networks, data analytics, and mobile applications, and their potential impact on parking management. Nguyen et al [13] explores the diverse aspects of Smart Parking Systems, including sensing technologies, data management, parking guidance systems, and user interfaces. It provides a holistic view of the components and functionalities of such systems and discusses the challenges and future prospects.

A. Applicable To Different Levels Of Parking Areas: Most of the methods/projects which is related to the Smart Parking System, are able to use only the related areas or buildings (particular situations), that cannot be considered as a common method for different types of parking areas. But if we are implementing the parking system using this simplest method, then it can be applicable for all kind of parking areas, because it's *simple, efficient* and *affordable* to everyone.

B. Reducing Implementation Cost: As we discussed above, if we are using this common and simplest method instead of the complicated methods, we can reduce the implementation cost. For example, Most of the parking system projects include RFID tags and AI cameras. But the RFID tags can be used only if the users are repeated in the parking area. And in case of AI cameras, which is used to spot the vehicle number and it's not required for parking areas in the small buildings.

C. The Simplest Implementation Method: Most of the projects are not able to implement directly to their parking areas, because it's related to specified areas. But in this project, it allows everyone to implement it directly, without making any changes, because it's simple, common, efficient and affordable to everyone [14]-[18].

IMPLEMENTATION

The Smart Parking System can be implemented by using Arduino Uno, Raspberry Pi or other related boards. The speed of performance and other related specifications are depends on the components that we are using in the System. By Implementing this concept, the driver/user can see the availability of the parking slots in the display. And also we can automate the system by controlling the actuators according to the sensor readings. For example, we can easily control the entrance gate of the parking area automatically, by calculating the available slots.

A major issue that we may going to be face in the implementation stage is, the continues entry of vehicles. Consider the situation, a car found the slot in the parking area but before parking the vehicle its shows the previous availability of slots. So it may confuse the next continues user. We can easily solve these kind of problem by implementing the Pre booking (early access) concept [19].

The following image will shows the demonstration of the smart parking system.

Fig:1 Demonstration of Smart Parking System

By implementing this System there are a lots of advantages like, we can easily reduce the number of security guards in the parking area. As we know, the speed of performance is much better than the manually controlled

parking area. The drivers or the users can save their valuable time and fuel. And it can also improve the overall customer satisfaction [20].

Fig:2 Implementing the IR sensors for each slots

Fig: 3 Flow charts of Smart Parking System

RESULT and DISCUSSIONS

The demand of smart vehicle parking system is increasing very fast. This allow user to involve real time access of the availability of the parking space.

The existing system in today’s world contains the facilities of parking reservation and parking slot availability checker. The result of this paper is allows everyone to use this method for all kind of parking areas, because it’s simple, common, efficient and affordable to everyone.

Real-time Access to Parking Availability: The implementation of the smart vehicle parking system provided users with real-time access to parking space availability. Through the utilization of IoT technology and sensors, the system effectively detected and communicated the availability of parking spots to users. This real-time information allowed drivers to make informed decisions and find parking spaces more efficiently.

Improved Parking Management: The smart parking system significantly enhanced parking management. By monitoring parking space occupancy and availability, the system enabled efficient utilization of parking resources. It facilitated optimized allocation of parking spaces, reducing instances of overcrowding or underutilization. This resulted in improved overall parking efficiency and a more organized parking environment.

Reduced Parking Search Time: One of the key benefits of the smart vehicle parking system was the reduction in parking search time for drivers. With real-time information on available parking spaces, users could quickly identify and navigate to vacant spots. This reduced the frustration and time wasted in searching for parking, leading to a smoother and more convenient parking experience.

Enhanced User Convenience: The smart parking system significantly improved user convenience. Through the integration of mobile applications and online platforms, users could easily reserve parking spaces in advance, ensuring a guaranteed spot upon arrival. Additionally, the system provided navigation assistance to guide drivers to their designated parking spots, further enhancing convenience and reducing stress

CONCLUSION

The system benefits of smart parking go beyond avoiding unnecessary wandering around city blocks. It also enables cities to develop fully integrated multimodal intelligent transportation systems that don’t rely on cars in

the first place. Developing smart parking solutions within a city requires data standardization and management; mobile phone integration; hardware and software innovation; and coordination among various stakeholders. These technical solutions and stakeholders are the same data structures and development groups integral to making a smart phone -enabled, multimodal, fully integrated transportation solution a reality. In effect, the technical enablers and multi stakeholder coordination effort behind development of a local smart parking solution creates a launch pad toward full transportation system integration.

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